

THE IMAGE OF A WOMAN IN THE NOVELS OF PEARL BUCK

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Abstract: P. Buck's novels are a significant contribution to world literature, especially with regard to the depiction of Chinese culture and women. This aspect is key to understanding the social norms and cultural expectations that have existed in China over a period of time. The study of the images of Chinese women in the novels of P. Buck is of current importance, as it allows us to dive more deeply into the world of their life and ideas.

Key words: Female, image, aristocratic, women, family, society, portrayal

INTRODUCTION

The portrayal of Chinese women in P. Buck's novels is a subject of interest and significance. The purpose of this article is to provide a brief overview of the theme and its importance in Buck's work, explain the relevance of studying the image of Chinese women in her literature, identify and describe the various Chinese female characters presented in her novels, and explore how these characters reflect social norms and cultural expectations of Chinese women of that period.

METHODS

In the novels of P. Buck we are faced with various images of Chinese women—from simple village girls to the highest members of aristocratic society. Each character has his own unique destiny, but they all reflect certain social realities of the time: the

status of a woman, her role in the family and society, as well as the expectations placed on her.

A writer who spent a significant part of her life in China, which greatly influenced her work. Her novels often revolve around themes related to China, including its culture, society and people. The portrayal of Chinese women is particularly significant as it provides insight into their roles, struggles, aspirations and challenges they faced during that time.

RESULTS

Studying the portrayal of Chinese women in P. Buck's novels allows us to better understand the historical context in which they lived and the changes that have occurred in social norms and cultural expectations as Chinese society has developed. In addition, studying these images broadens our understanding of the diversity of women's experiences and helps us think about gender issues in new ways.

Another reason the study of the image of Chinese women in Buck's novels is relevant for several reasons. First, it allows us to gain a deeper understanding of the lives of Chinese women during this era—their social status, family dynamics, educational opportunities or lack thereof, marriage customs, etc. Second, it provides an authentic portrayal that goes against stereotypes or misconceptions about Chinese women that were common at the time or even today.

DISCUSSION

In P. Buck's novels we meet characters such as Zhu Lin, the daughter of a wealthy landowner, who is forced to go through numerous trials; Xue Tai is a brave and adventurous girl; Ya Mi is a humble servant facing the difficulties of her social status. Each of these women has her own character and destiny, but together they help us understand many aspects of Chinese life.

Buck's works feature a wide range of female characters who represent different facets of Chinese women's lives: a) O-Lan from *The Good Earth*: O-Lan is portrayed as hardworking and resilient despite facing many challenges as a rural woman in pre-revolutionary China. b) Madame Wu from *The Pavilion of Women*: Madame Wu

challenges traditional gender roles by seeking independence in her marriage while challenging society's expectations. c) Mei-len from *Dragon Seed*: Mei-len embodies strength as she courageously fights against the Japanese invasion along with other peasant women.

Chinese women in P. Buck's novels reflect various aspects of the social norms and cultural expectations of the time. Zhu Lin, for example, is forced to go through numerous trials in the struggle to maintain her honor and dignity, which emphasizes the importance of virginity for women of that time. Xue Tai portrays the image of an independent and adventurous girl who violates the standards of behavior for women, which causes disapproval from society. Ya Mi is an example of a humble servant who faces harassment and abuse from her employers.

These female characters reflect the social norms and cultural expectations imposed on Chinese women during this period. They depict traditional gender roles assigned to women - their responsibilities in the home, subordination to men, and limited opportunities for education or personal growth. However, Buck also emphasizes their resilience, resourcefulness, and ability to change in the face of these social constraints.

CONCLUSION

Studying the images of Chinese women in P. Buck's novels allows us to see how social norms and cultural expectations limited the lives and choices of women of that time. It also helps us think about what changes have taken place today and what gender issues we still need to address.

In conclusion, the portrayal of Chinese women in P. Buck's novels provides valuable information about their lives, struggles, aspirations and expectations of society at that time. Studying these images helps challenge stereotypes and at the same time provides a deeper understanding of the experiences of Chinese women. By exploring the various female characters in her works, readers will gain a deeper understanding of the complexity of gender dynamics and cultural norms in Chinese society.

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